

G'AYBULLA AS-SALOM IS A SCIENTIST WHO MADE A GREAT CONTRIBUTION TO THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF TRANSLATION STUDIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, G'aybulla As-Salom who was a great translator and a great professor, and we have inherited his great translations, his scientific activities, all his good works, which have been inherited by us, and the things that will be covered are his life and creativity, all the scientific works he has done and the places where he worked, all the titles and scientific activities of our teacher G'aybulla As-Salom. All scientific works and phrases written by him are also covered.

Keywords: Life and work of G'aybulla As-Salom, scientific works, titles, scientific activities, expressions, professors, translation.

If two people exchange one apple each, each gets one apple. But two people exchange one new idea each, each person will have two ideas. Literary translation belongs to this second type of exchange. It is known from history that the peoples of Central Asia have made many achievements in science since time immemorial. In particular, the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek, which has a great place in the science of the 20th century, is a place that has produced great scholars in the cradle of world science. Already, Mirzo Ulug'bek National University of Uzbekistan during its activity made a significant contribution to the development of education and science, as well as to the training of personnel for various branches of the republic's economy, social and spiritual spheres. In the past period, more than 100 academicians and 2,500 doctors of science and candidates were trained. T. Sarimsaqov, S. Sirojiddinov, M. Salohiddinov schools of mathematicians, J. Musayev, biochemists, H. Abdullayev, T. Dolimov geologists schools are widely recognized. Heroes of Uzbekistan A. Oripov, E. Vohidov, O. Sharafiddinov and S. G'aniyev received education at the university. Turkistan Peoples University, Tutkistan Muslim, Peoples Dorilfununi, Turkistan State University, Central Asian State University, Tashkent State University many scientists and writers wrote and translated works that left an indelible mark in history at the university named after the National University of Uzbekistan. In addition, the theory of literary translation was founded in this study.

G'aybulla As-Salom, who made his main contribution to the development of the theory of translation throughout the republic, has a significant place in this front. A well-known literary critic, scholar of translation, doctor of philology, professor, scientist who has served the republic, the owner of a big heart G'aybulla As-Salom (pseudonym), real name Salomov G'aybulla Tajiddinovich on December 11 1932 Khatirchi Samarkand region was born in the district (now this district belongs to Navoi region). Nazira Salomova, one of her daughters, says about her father. Father G'aybulla As-Salom grew up with special devotion to learning from childhood. He knew Arabic and Russian languages. He was the only child in the family. Therefore he started working from the 7th grade. He graduated from two schools at the same time. After that, in 1952 he entered the Faculty of Philology of Samarkand State University and

those who graduated in 1956. Fathers of G'aybulla As-Salom Tajiddin Mullah the master of this time was one of the individuals. He was strict and demanding in his upbringing. Teacher mentions the following about them in his book "O Dear Life" "Our father was known as Mulla Taji among the el- ulus. They were educated and respectable people who studied in the old school. But our father lived his whole life afraid of being a nationalist," enemy of the people" 'Ear'. Taji is not a name it's a nickname, Uzbek culture is bad for the soul, after all, it hurts if you don't say it. During 1956-1957, G'aybulla As-Salom worked as a graduate researcher, deputy director at the Institute of language and Literature of the Soviet Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In 1967-1969 he worked as the deputy editor-in-chief of "Uzbek Encyclopedia" and from student 1969, he also worked as the head of the Department of Translation Theory of Tashkent State University. He continued the main part of his work at this university. Until the last years of his life, he taught young people about science, the theory of translation, its importance as a science, and its history and he conducted his scientific research and mentored many students. G'aybulla As-Salom scientific and creative activity is devoted to issues of spirituality culture and enlightenment.

As a result of this scientific and creative activity, G'aybulla As-salom published a number of literature. His first studies began while he was still studying at Samarkand University. In 1961 teacher pamphlets such as "Translation of proverbs and idioms" "lexical and phraseological issues of artistic translation", "Translation of proverbs and proverbs from Russian to Uzbek" were published in 1964 by "Fan" publishing house. During these years he wrote mature scientific works on the issues of lexicography and encyclopedia. Then successively "Introduction to the theory of translation" Translators skills" "Bridges of friendship" (co-authored with N. Komilov) "Problems of literary translation and literary history" Literary tradition and problems of literary translation Textbooks and monographs entitled Fundamentals of Translation Theory were published. In these works, pure and consistent theoretical ideas about literary translation, translators skills and art are presented. Actual scientific problems were solved during the comparative study of translations of literature created in several languages. Of course, along with these literature he presented scientific manuals as a program to the higher educational institutions of the republic. In particular, in 1973 "Course on history of translation" "Introductory course on theory of translation", it has published a series of programs such as "Basics of general translation theory course program". G'aybulla As-Salom in the program "Basics of general theory of translation course program" on the topic translation and style, the following thoughts on the basic concepts of style: "The concept of style - human. The heart of the writer is style. Style is the indicator of the writers "own voice" - he emphasizes.

He presented to the public books in the spirit of teaching, not limited to many scientific works. In particular teacher work "Nightingale" one important point: "For some reason, some of our linguists, literary scholars and translators should be punished... If not, they should be forced to read their books aloud in public. There is no worse the listener will be drowsy as heavy as lead... The sharp penmanship of teacher G'aybulla As-Salom is reflected in his thoughts and Zikr, comments and observations about language in his work "Language and life":

The strangeness of the language is from the poverty of thought.

What can you do if you don't have a tongue ?

The Bisot language of many of our linguists consists of a complex of terms. They do not exist outside of this bisot.

If this scientific book is translated into human language, all its meaning and effect will be lost. There will be no science greetings.

Our language, according to its composition, is similar to the "Pakhtakor" team left.

Don't forget your birthday, but don't forget why you were born.

He who drags others down does not realize that he is sinking into the depths of the earth.

G'aybulla As-Salom trained many students during his creative career. Together with the teacher, the mature people of their time were shoulder to shoulder in the process of creation. Among his students, many academicians, professors and scientists, doctors of science have been contributing to the development of science. Professor, winner of the Beruni Prize, doctor of philology E.A Karimov expresses his opinion about teacher: G'aybulla As-Salom is a master of knowledge in all aspects. He has a widely recognized school, great students, books, pamphlets, textbooks and pulpits he created with his own hands. G'aybulla As-Salom is a prolific translation scholar. The volume of his scientific researches consists of 278.7 printed plates (methodology, literary, journalism, practical translation, and works related to artistic creativity are not included in this calculation). This is a word for set of scientific books (monographs) consisting of about 28 volumes, each consisting of 10 printed plates. In other words, since 1954, he regularly produced scientific products in 9.6 printing plates every year. Since 1970 the number of dissertations defended under his supervision (opponent) reaches 63. This means that every year, the master scientist gave an official guarantee to almost three doctors of science, professors and candidates of science. G'aybulla As-Salom describes his creative path as follows: "With luck, it will be just a prelude to my greatest scientific and creative work. I dream of creating a Turkic dictionary, a translation textbook, a multilingual Maghreb "Mashriq devon" (antology), a poetry collection, and a research devoted to the analysis of translations of the Holy Qur'an...

During the years of independence, teacher aimed to write 25 volumes of books and during 1997 he managed to publish only two of these works "Ey umri aziz and Ezgulikka chog'lan odamzod". The reason is that at the big event held in connection with the granting of the "National" status to the current Mirzo Ulug'bek National University on 31st of 2000 in January due to a heart attack the teacher was followed to his last destination from this place. However, in many social networks, in particular, on You Tube and Google platforms, the date of death of the teacher is referred to as 2003 with some errors. However, on January 28, 2000 the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov granted the status of National to the National University named after Mirzo Ulug'bek. The theory of artistic translation created by us young people G'aybulla As-Salom is scientific to continue school, to discover new scientific directions must today it is important to perpetuate the name of G'aybulla As-Salom is one of the issues. For this purpose, as a proposal Foreign of G'aybulla organization of a scientific-practical conference of dedicate talented students is appropriate.

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